

Implementation of an Integrated Standard and Generalized Perturbation Theory Module within an SP_n Reactor Core Computation Code

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents an Uncertainty Quantification module implemented within an SPN PWR core computation code. Use of first-order Standard (SPT) and Generalized (GPT) Perturbation Theories enabled its successful application to full scale cores, after validation was performed by comparison with the TRIPOLI Monte Carlo code on the UMZONE critical mock-up experiment, and on the KAIST numerical benchmark. SPT and GPT calculations and associated SU (sensitivity and uncertainty) analysis were performed for both keff and reaction rate distributions. For the purpose of meeting industrial performance and robustness constraints, including ease of use, some distinctive features were built in. The code is highly encapsulated and automates the production of consistent neutronic input data from a user defined perturbation. Furthermore, specific care was taken in reducing data storage and transfers, which typically constitute a major bound for uncertainty studies, while preserving a failure-safe algorithm.

Keywords: Uncertainty quantification, Perturbation Theory, Industrial reactor code

1. INTRODUCTION

Uncertainty analyses are increasingly being used in nuclear engineering (neutron dosimetry, reactor design, criticality assessments, etc.) to deduce the accuracy of selected predicted observables (fast fluence, reactivity coefficients, criticality, etc.) and contribute to establish performance and safety margins. They provide confidence intervals prior to direct measurement, hence proving of particular importance in the lack thereof (*e.g.* for new designs), and furthermore allow weighting the contribution of each error source so as to orient uncertainty reduction efforts.

While model bias has to be estimated by comparison to a reference scheme (usually Monte-Carlo), and numerical error can be controlled by generic scientific computation methods, evaluating the effect of input data uncertainty usually requires problem-specific algorithms. In the present article, we expose the implementation of an Industrial Perturbation module performing the latter uncertainty propagation from nuclear data in the context of an industrial neutronics core computation code.

In view of meeting production performance and maintainability criteria, this module was built around three main features:

- A built-in compatibility with the inner data of the Industrial SP_n neutronic solver, so as to avoid any performance or information loss due to copy, cast or operation duplication. A particular care was taken in the memory management of perturbed cross-section fields.

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Figure 1. General uncertainty quantification workflow. I. Uncertainty of input data are modelled as random variables, typically multi-gaussian for nuclear data. II. a) The nominal input data are perturbed; b) a (possibly simplified) computation model for the observable is run; c) the statistical properties of the observable are deduced by post-treatment. III. By varying the input perturbation, the sensitivity of the observable with respect to each input can be compared.

- An implementation of Standard and Generalized Perturbation Theory, allowing for efficient uncertainty propagation for generic observables, with a very high scalability with respect to the number of uncertain input data.
- An integrated and mostly automated workflow between the uncertain microscopic data specification and the observable uncertainty. In particular, preservation of functional dependencies between inputs is granted (*e.g.* a variation of an isotopic scattering cross-section automatically translates into appropriate variations of the macroscopic total and scattering cross-sections).

The module structure parallels the workflow depicted in step II. of figure 1, detailed in figure 2, with three submodules, one per sub-task: uncertain data definition, uncertainty propagation, post-treatment.

After a brief theoretical summary in section 2, we will successively present each submodule and its tasks. In section 3, the user interface for specifying which data uncertainty to compute is detailed, including the automated input cross-sections consistency mechanism and memory management. Section 4 is devoted to the propagation problem resolution within the different implemented methods, comprising first order finite-difference, and standard and generalized perturbation theory. The raw output of the implemented methods having no direct statistical meaning, they must be complemented with data variance and covariance matrices to translate to output variances and confidence intervals. This post-treatment is not detailed here for conciseness. Validation of the module will be exposed in section 5, before we summarize our results and outline future developments in section 6.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND FOR UNCERTAINTY PROPAGATION

2.1. Uncertainty Propagation Problem Definition

The general problem of uncertainty propagation, visually summarized in figure 1, can be formulated in terms of an observable $y \in \mathbb{R}$ which depends on a set of input data $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, treated as continuous random variables admitting joint probability density $p(x)$. In principle, the problem then amounts to finding the probability

density $q(y)$ of $y = f(x)$, or in practice at least its first two moments,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{y} &= \mathbb{E}(y) = \int dx p(x) f(x) \\ \Delta y^2 &= \text{Var}(y) = \int dx p(x) (f(x) - \bar{y})^2\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

These quantities may be estimated by sampling the probability distribution p with a finite set of input data of size P , followed by P full neutronics computations. This stochastic approach has the merit of converging towards the exact values of targeted quantities, and of allowing for the simultaneous study of arbitrarily many scalar observables. However its computational cost makes it unfit for typical industrial applications, such as criticality uncertainty quantification.

2.2. Deterministic Methods

Let us instead Taylor expand the output at first order around the nominal value of the input,

$$y = f(x_0) + \sum_{i=1}^n \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial x^i} \right|_{x_0} (x^i - x_0^i) + o(x - x_0), \text{ with } x_0 = \mathbb{E}(x)$$

one then finds,

$$\bar{y} = y_0 = f(x_0), \quad \Delta y^2 = S^T C S, \quad \text{with } \begin{cases} S_i = \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial x^i} \right|_{x_0} \\ C_{ij} = \text{Cov}(x^i, x^j) = \mathbb{E}((x^i - x_0^i)(x^j - x_0^j)) \end{cases}\tag{2}$$

Given the nominal values x_0 and the corresponding covariance matrix C , the only quantities to compute are the partial derivatives around the nominal value $\left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial x^i} \right|_{x_0}$. The resulting workflow is represented in figure 2. We implemented three sensitivity computation methods.

- Finite differences and Exact Perturbation Theory [?]
- First-Order Standard Perturbation Theory (SPT) [?]
- Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) [?, ?]

3. PERTURBATION DEFINITION SUBMODULE

The Perturbation module implements the three aforementioned deterministic methods. Neutronics computation options and data to be perturbed (step 1 in figure 2) are freely chosen by the user. The first Perturbation submodule carries next step (step 2) of generating the corresponding inputs for the perturbation solver yielding the perturbed output (full neutronics computation or perturbation theory). Its main features will be presented in the following order:

- generation of consistent perturbed solver inputs
- memory management of the perturbed data
- supported forms of input perturbations

3.1. Perturbed data generation

A core computation naturally depends on each nuclear data needed to describe all possible reactions for each isotope present in the core. However, the Boltzmann equation strongly condenses this information and our

Figure 2. Structure of the Perturbation module and its submodules. The module is written in C++, for compatibility with the Industrial neutronics solver and therefore better performance. In the Industrial code a Python layer is used as an interface for users, hence a binding of the Perturbation module in Python. All tasks not automated yet are hence written in the Python layer.

solver directly depends on only four macroscopic quantities, namely the scattering, fission and total cross sections, and the equivalent fission spectrum, possibly indexed by space, energy and angle coordinates. As one may perturb quantities at any level in this process, a practical module requires an automated mechanism to produce consistent perturbed Boltzmann data.

To this end the InputPerturbation submodule operates several distinctions (see Figure 3):

- *microscopic data* are the microscopic cross-sections and concentrations defined for one isotope;
- *macroscopic data* are the isotopic macroscopic cross-sections and their sums.

Besides,

- *isotopic data* are the data defined for one isotope;
- *aggregate data* are the cross sections summing all isotopic contributions, for one or several reaction.

Finally, logical categories are drawn specifically for the perturbation propagation problem,

- *direct variables* are the ones the user directly chooses to perturb (they can be isotopic or aggregate);
- *indirect variables* are the input variables of the perturbation computation solvers that depend on some direct variables. They are hence adjusted by the module InputPerturbation accordingly;
- *partial variables* of an indirect variable are the direct variables which affect it. The indirect variables are always aggregate in the Perturbation module, but the partial variables can be aggregate or isotopic¹.

For a given perturbation, direct perturbed data are computed first, and indirect variables are then deduced. For this process to be well-defined a direct variable cannot also be an indirect variable of some other direct data, and such perturbations are forbidden by the module.

¹For instance, the isotopic and aggregate excess sections are both partial variables of the total cross-section indirect variable.

Figure 3. Data categories and dependencies in the perturbed solver input generation.

3.2. Memory management of the perturbed data

All perturbed output computation methods take perturbed Boltzmann data as their input. On the other hand, the industrial code reliability demands that the Perturbation module does not affect other functionalities, so that in particular it can not be allowed to modify the nominal sections. This leads to a coexistence of nominal and perturbed data, which can raise memory requirements issues.

A perturbed indirect variable $\Sigma_p^{(red)}$ is therefore computed from its partial variables as,

$$\Sigma_p^{(red)} = \Sigma_0^{(red)} + \sum_i (\Sigma_p^{(par),i} - \Sigma_0^{(par),i}) = \Sigma_0^{(red)} + \sum_i (\alpha_i - 1) \Sigma_0^{(par),i} \quad (3)$$

The storage of perturbed partial variables is hence avoided.

Besides, perturbations can actually be computed from section differences, $d_p \Sigma^{(red)} = \Sigma_p^{(red)} - \Sigma_0^{(red)}$. When the perturbation is localized, *e.g.* acts on only one energy group, then $d_p \Sigma^{(red)}$ contains many null values, paving the way for further compression.

3.3. Supported forms of input perturbations

The nuclear data whose perturbations can be studied with the module all eventually contribute to macroscopic cross-sections which feed the neutronics solver. In order to minimize the input perturbation propagation process, the perturbation is actually performed only at the Boltzmann data level.

These data are either EnergySpatialFields or scatteringCrossSection field. Besides, in the scattering cross-sections the final energy group and angular moment are correlated, but this data is currently not provided by standard nuclear data libraries, preventing non-uniform perturbations in these coordinates. Therefore, available perturbations are of the following forms:

- uniform in space and energy: $\Sigma_r \rightarrow \Sigma_r(g, \mathbf{r}) * \alpha_r$
- uniform in space, varying in energy: $\Sigma_r \rightarrow \Sigma_r(g, \mathbf{r}) * \alpha_r(g)$
- varying in space, uniform in energy: $\Sigma_r \rightarrow \Sigma_r(g, \mathbf{r}) * \alpha_r(\mathbf{r})$
- varying in space and energy: $\Sigma_r \rightarrow \Sigma_r(g, \mathbf{r}) * \alpha_r(g, \mathbf{r})$

where the group index g refers to the final energy in the case of scattering cross-sections.

4. UNCERTAINTY POSTPROCESSING SUBMODULE

While the sensitivities alone provide useful physical information on the core, for the purpose of uncertainty quantification the input data uncertainties must be factored in via covariance matrices. The output variance is then computed by Eq. 2, and statistical quantities such as confidence intervals can be deduced from it provided some assumptions on the input data probability distributions (typically Gaussian for nuclear data).

Assuming no correlations between different isotopes, the global covariance matrix consists in the covariance matrices for each isotope (i),

$$C^{(i)} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{r_1, r_1}^{(i)} & \cdots & C_{r_1, r_m}^{(i)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{r_1, r_m}^{(i)} & \cdots & C_{r_m, r_m}^{(i)} \end{pmatrix}, \text{ with } C_{r_q, r_p}^{(i)} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{r_q, r_p; 1, 1}^{(i)} & \cdots & C_{r_q, r_p; 1, G}^{(i)} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ C_{r_q, r_p; G, 1}^{(i)} & \cdots & C_{r_q, r_p; G, G}^{(i)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

for m reaction types and G energy groups.

When the number of groups in the nuclear data library is different from the number of groups used for the uncertainty study, a condensation step is performed. For instance, assuming that the departure energy mesh g is a subdivision of the arrival mesh g_c , neglecting flux uncertainties leads to,

$$C_{r_q, r_p; g_c, g'_c}^{(i)} = \frac{\sum_{g \in [g_c, g'_c]} \sum_{g' \in [g_c, g'_c]} C_{r_q, r_p; g, g'}^{(i)} \Phi_g \Phi_{g'}}{\sum_{g \in [g_c, g'_c]} \sum_{g' \in [g_c, g'_c]} \Phi_g \Phi_{g'}} \quad (5)$$

with Φ the lattice calculation scalar flux computed with the departure energy mesh. An alternative procedure based on uncertainty conservation, replacing the flux by sensitivities, was also tested and lead to very close results [?].

This step was incorporated in our study to convert the 36 energy groups COMAC [?] matrices into 8 energy groups matrices. At the moment this process is written in the Python user layer, but it should be encapsulated and automated by a C++ submodule in the near future.

5. RESULTS VALIDATION AND PERFORMANCE

The Perturbation module has been validated against reference Monte-Carlo computations from TRIPOLI4 [?] on the EPICURE UMZONE experimental core configuration [?]. This study established that on almost all data the relative difference in sensitivities was below 10%.

Two exceptions to this general situation were observed for:

- sections with very small values, such as (n, xn) reactions
- or for reactions with strong resonances, such as capture, which displayed differences up to 50%, depending on the transport modelization options.

The latter limitation is most probably due to strong self-shielding effects, which can only be accounted for by including the lattice computation step into the perturbation process. This currently falls beyond the scope of the presented module.

We furthermore conducted a sensitivity analysis on the AIEA 3D test core KAIST [?]. A sample of obtained results is shown in table I.

In this case, we see the sensitivities of the criticality parameter k to nuclear data on several isotopes, for different reactions. The core is at 15% of its nominal power and all control rods are inserted.

Table I. Sensitivities of the criticality k value for different isotopes and reactions (in %/%).

	^{235}U	^{238}U	Zr_{nat}	^{10}B (sol.)	H_2O
capture	-3.91×10^{-2}	-2.07×10^{-1}	-6.82×10^{-3}	-1.19×10^{-1}	-2.60×10^{-2}
fission	2.19×10^{-1}	5.96×10^{-2}	0	0	0
scattering	1.09×10^{-4}	8.11×10^{-3}	4.83×10^{-3}	7.83×10^{-6}	2.62×10^{-1}

Performance of the Perturbation module can be evaluated by comparing its execution time to a standard neutronics computation. In our case, computing the nominal state, *via* a critical boron search, took 55% of the total execution time. The Perturbation module initialisation took 31%, almost exclusively for the adjoint flux eigenvector computation. Then, computing 20 sensitivities took only 5.90%, that is approximately 0.25% per perturbation, which clearly highlights the computational benefit of first-order Perturbation Theory.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this article we have presented a Perturbation module embedded within an industrial SP_N core computation code. By implementing first-order Perturbation Theory methods it opens the way to time-efficient uncertainty quantification or sensitivity studies from nuclear data, for systems up to the scale of industrial cores.

Three structural features of this module are:

- a coupling with the inner parts of the neutronics solver, for higher accuracy and minimized data treatment and conversion issues,
- an implementation of first-order Standard and Generalized Perturbation Theory, which are very efficient for dealing with many uncertain inputs,
- a high level of encapsulation, in particular regarding the generation of consistent sets of perturbed input data.

We have been able to validate the results of this module, both on the UMZONE and KAIST numerical cores, and confirm it displays the expected time-profile.

There are many different ways in which the module can be upgraded in the future. Regarding the user interface, the encapsulation of statistical post-treatments and covariance matrices condensation would constitute a natural step forward. A more ambitious development would be the automation of input perturbation for some specific purposes, typically uncertainty sources discrimination and quantification, which could be achieved by coupling to a platform like OpenTurns.

The functionalities of the module can also be extended. Allowing for the computation of different observables with the GPT should be rather straightforward. One may think *e.g.* of the axial offset, the fraction of delayed neutrons, or the delayed neutrons lifetime.

In view of encompassing the fullest possible set of theoretical uncertainties, the admissible perturbations on input data should be extended as well. Concentrations will be included in the very near future. Perturbations of input other than nuclear data is envisioned. The effect of the state of the core can in principle already be studied, but should be encapsulated by the Perturbation module for usability. Besides, perturbations of the geometry, modelling for instance technological uncertainty on components dimensions, or inserted rod position, can be made to fit in the current framework as well.

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